

A MIXED-METHODS ANALYSIS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF RESEARCH MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES IN BASIC EDUCATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 3

Pages: 283-288

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2464

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13902717

Manuscript Accepted: 08-30-2024

A Mixed-Methods Analysis on the Implementation of Research Management Guidelines in Basic Education

Jessa Marie Lianne C. Balindres,* Garry C. Cachuela

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This descriptive study aimed in finding out the implementation of Research Management Guidelines of schools in the basic education. The independent variables focused on the teachers' educational attainment and rank while the level of implementation of the research management guidelines as the dependent variable. The participants of the study were the 140 elementary teachers of the District of Calinog II chosen through random sampling answered the survey instrument and 7 out of the 140 participants responded in the interview to gather the qualitative data. The quantitative data was analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples and One Way Analysis of Variance as statistical tools. The level of significance was set at 0.05 alpha. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data. The findings of this study revealed that the level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education as an entire group and when classified as to educational attainment and rank was average. There is a significant difference in the level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education when the respondents were classified as to educational attainment. There is no significant difference in the level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education when the respondents were classified as to rank. The difficulties they encountered in the implementation of the research management guidelines: (1) Limited Knowledge in Research; (2) Much Workload; (3) Overlapping Activities and; (4) Lack of Resources. Thus, a training program in research is highly encouraged.

Keywords: *implementation, research, management, guidelines*

Introduction

The Basic Education Governance Act of 2001 accentuates the role of research in the management and administration of the basic education system with a mandate to strive in strengthening research in basic education. Such efforts include various research initiatives under the Basic Education Research Agenda (BERA).

The issuance of DepED Order 16 s. 2017, the Research Management Guideline gives a clear path on how to conduct research in basic education in the Philippine public-school setting. The research initiative in the Department of Education sustains its progressive orientation by ensuring that actions made through the integration of policies and programs were guided by sound, relevant and evidence-based process through the conduct of research.

In this connection, the creation of the Policy Research Division (PRD) was created under the Rationalization Plan promotes and oversees the vertical and horizontal conduct of education research in the department across all governance level to conduct, support, and manage empirical studies, and thereby promote evidence-based decision and policy-making at various levels.

A study conducted by Biruk (2013) in Ethiopia affirmed that only a few teachers conducted research studies, because of the lack of teachers' research skills and expertise. Although the teacher-participants held a positive attitude towards research, their participation and contribution were reported to be low. Factors like lack of research knowledge, insufficient research training programs for teachers to enhance and develop their research skills, and lack of reference materials limited them from doing research. Doing research simply tries to put theories into application and practice, where teachers examine themselves and analyse the kind of teaching context they are in (McNiff, 2010). Furthermore, classroom research does not only bridge the gap between theories and practice (Johnson, 2012), it also gives teachers professional skills in research, which is crucial for a transformative education (Hine & Lavery, 2014).

In the educational point of view, research extends beyond having an impressive reward for it develops both education practitioner's and students critical thinking skills, analytical ability, and communication skills that are needed to become globally competitive. Educational research grows its popularity in the advent of the implementation of the K to 12 curricula for it highlights the importance of connecting knowledge with practical application. In order to function well in educational endeavors, research becomes the lifeblood of operation to become effective and efficient in the quest of providing basic quality education.

This study was mainly anchored in the Theory of Constructivism by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky and the Framework of 21st Century Learning. The theory of Constructivism represents one of the big ideas in education (Bada, 2015). According to Patella and Madrigal (2017) it was the anchor of the study because its objective was not to set standards but to look into probable areas for the improvement of teachers based on the given standards aided by their learning experiences. Primarily, educational reforms aimed for all students to succeed (Bada, 2015). Conducting research is believed to contribute mainly in the development and improvement of the teaching and learning situation and finding solutions to problems encountered by students and teachers in schools.

Furthermore, this is also anchored on the framework that skills, knowledge and expertise students must master to succeed in work and

life which are the 21st century learning skills that must be acquired by learners. It is a blend of content of knowledge, specific skills, expertise and literacies. Additionally, this enables the 21st century professional learning communities for teachers that model the kind of classroom learning that promote the 21st century skills and the role of the teachers to teach the students (Bada, 2015). Research is one of the 21st century skills that must be possess by teachers. this will enable them to improve their teaching as well as to improve the teaching and learning environment in their school.

With the aforementioned ideas stated above, it will be in this premise that the researchers would like to investigate the level of implementation of research in basic education based on educational attainment and rank, identify the common difficulties encountered by the teachers in the implementation of Research Management Guidelines and eventually propose a training program for teachers based on the findings of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed mixed method to investigate the objective of the study. Hence, mixed methods research combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a more comprehensive understanding of complex research problems. By integrating numerical data with in-depth exploration, researchers leverage the strengths of both methodologies. This approach enables more robust conclusions and a fuller understanding of the research question.

Participants

The participants of this study were the 140 randomly selected elementary teachers of the District of Calinog II for School Year 2022-2023. They were classified as to educational attainment and rank. As to educational attainment, they were classified as to master's degree, and baccalaureate degree. As to rank, they were classified as to Teacher I, II, II and Master Teachers and Head Teachers.

In the conduct of the qualitative data gathering, seven participants (1 teacher with finished research, 2 teachers with approved proposal, and 4 teachers that are encouraged to conduct research) were selected to undergo interview in the challenges they encountered in the implementation of the research management guidelines.

Instrument

The data gathering instruments that were used in this study were a researcher-made instrument which were divided into three parts. Part I gathered information about the participants' personal data which include their names (optional), educational attainment and rank; Part II was a questionnaire which solicited ideas regarding the respondents' implementation of research management guidelines; Part III was the interview guide that gathered qualitative responses on the common difficulties encountered by the teachers in the implementation of Research Management Guidelines.

The implementation of research management guidelines instrument used for this study was validated by experts in the field of research in West Visayas State University – Lambunao Campus and was pilot-tested from Schools District of Calinog I, Calinog, Iloilo. The result of pilot-test was subjected to reliability test using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The coefficient alpha (or Cronbach's alpha) is used to assess the internal consistency of the item. Based on the result of the pilot-test, the questionnaire had 0.964 reliability coefficient. If the alpha value is .70 or higher, the instrument is considered reliable (Statistics Solutions, 2023).

Procedure

Permission was secured from the Division Office of the Schools Division of Iloilo. After granting the permit, the Principals and School Heads of the different elementary schools in the District of Calinog II were informed through pertinent documents.

On the quantitative part, the researchers personally explained and administered the questionnaires to the respondents. After which the data were collected, processed, and were subjected to the pertinent statistical tools using SPSS.

But in the qualitative, the participants were encouraged to take part during the event of gathering data. The researchers employed one on one interview and follow up questions via messenger. This is done in order to have an in-depth understanding of the difficulties they encounter in the implementation of research guidelines.

The participants were identified purposively based on the result of the questionnaire given. They were personally asked of their willingness to participate in the study and were asked to sign a letter of consent.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis. The following statistical tools were used to analyze and to interpret the data:

The Mean was used to determine the level of implementation of research management guidelines.

The Standard Deviation was used to determine the homogeneity and/or heterogeneity of the respondents' responses on the level of implementation of research management guidelines from the mean. It was also used for inferential data analysis.

The t-test for independent samples was used to determine the differences in the level of implementation of research management guidelines of the respondents when classified as to educational attainment while One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used when the respondents were classified as to rank. The level of significance was set at .05 alpha.

Qualitative Data Analysis. The data gathered were subjected to thematic analysis of data. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to a set of texts, such as interview transcripts. The researcher closely examines the data to identify common themes – topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly (Clarke & Braun, 2016).

Thematic analysis is a good approach to research where you're trying to find out something about people's views, opinions, knowledge, experiences or values from a set of qualitative data – for example, interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey responses. In this study, thematic analysis was used to determine the common difficulties encountered by the teachers in the implementation of research management guidelines.

Ethical Considerations

This study took into consideration the ethical standards in doing research. Primarily the prospective research participants were fully informed about the procedures involved in research and must give their consent to participate. Ethical standards also required the researcher to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the subject being studied. Almost all research guarantees the participants' confidentiality -- they were assured that identifying information would not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study. The stricter standard is the principle of anonymity which essentially means that the participant should remain anonymous throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Implementation of Research Management Guidelines of Schools in Basic Education as an Entire Group and when Classified as to Educational Attainment and Rank. The level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education as an entire group was average, $M=2.63$, $SD=0.79$.

When classified as to educational attainment, both the teachers with bachelor's degree ($M=2.55$, $SD=0.79$), and master's degree ($M=2.87$, $SD=0.73$) have average level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education.

Also, when classified as to rank, teachers with teacher I ($M=2.50$, $SD=0.84$), teacher II ($M=2.61$, $SD=0.71$), and teacher III ($M=2.72$, $SD=0.76$) as well as master and head teachers ($M=2.99$, $SD=0.55$) have average level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in the District of Calinog II.

The result further showed that regardless of educational attainment and rank the respondents showed the same level of perception towards the implementation of the research management guidelines. It might be for the reason that the participants may be aware of the implementation of research management guidelines but have not really embrace the culture of research.

Table 1 shows the data.

Table 1. *Level of Implementation of Research Management Guidelines of Schools in Basic Education as an Entire Group and when Classified as to Educational Attainment and Rank*

Category	SD	M	Description
Entire Group	0.79	2.63	Average
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree	0.79	2.55	Average
Master's Degree	0.73	2.87	Average
Rank			
Teacher I	0.84	2.50	Average
Teacher II	0.71	2.61	Average
Teacher III	0.76	2.72	Average
Master Teacher and Head Teacher	0.55	2.99	Average

Note: The description was based on the following scale: Very Low (1.00-1.49), Low (1.50-2.49), Average (2.50-3.49), High (3.50-4.49), Very High (4.50-5.00)

Difference in the Level of Implementation of Research Management Guidelines of Schools in Basic Education when the Respondents were Classified as to Educational Attainment and Rank. The data shows that there is a significant difference in the level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education when the respondents were classified as to educational attainment, $t(138)=-2.064$, $p=0.041$. This means that teachers who have master's degree have high level of implementation of the research management guidelines compared to teachers who are bachelor's degree holder.

The result of the study simply shows that perception towards the research management guidelines differ with level of educational attainment. It might be for the reason that, as one gains knowledge of research through continuous education the more insights they gain and the more they embrace research in their profession, thus the higher their level of perception. This idea agrees with the study

of Pellegrino and Hilton (2013) in which they concluded that educational attainment is a stronger predictor of competency. Teachers who are better educated have a broader sense of competency and better abilities to learn more from complex task training and that include research.

Table 2 shows the data.

Table 2. *Difference in the Level of Implementation of Research Management Guidelines of Schools in Basic Education when Classified as to Educational Attainment*

Category	t-value	df	p-value	Decision
Educational Attainment	-2.064*	138	0.041	Significant

*p-value<0.05

However, there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of research management guidelines of schools in basic education when the respondents were classified as to rank, $F(3,136)=2.204$, $p=0.090$. This means that teachers' level of implementation of the research management guidelines do not vary regardless of their rank.

The result showed that rank is not a factor to consider in the teacher's perception of management guidelines. This idea adheres with the statement of Barnes, du Plessis, and Frantz (2021) in which they stated that rank and research competency are not necessarily directly correlated. While rank or position within an academic or professional institution can indicate experience and expertise, research competency is determined by an individual's skills, knowledge, and abilities in conducting research effectively. While higher-ranked individuals may have had more opportunities to develop and demonstrate research competency through their academic and professional journey, research competency can be acquired and improved at any stage of one's career. It is a continuous learning process that involves ongoing skill development, staying up-to-date with research advancements, and actively engaging in scholarly activities.

Table 3 reveals the data.

Table 3. *Difference in the Level of Implementation of Research Management Guidelines of Schools in Basic Education when Classified as to Rank*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.951	3	1.317	2.204	.090
Within Groups	81.253	136	.597		
Total	85.204	139			

Common Difficulties Encountered by the Teachers in the Implementation of Research Management Guidelines. Research Management Guidelines has been established in order to encourage and help guide teachers to engage in research, since the Department of Education is considering that research is very vital in the improvement of the delivery of education. But, despite of these still teachers encountered difficulties in the implementation of this research guidelines.

Based on the qualitative data gathered from the purposively selected participants the following are the difficulties they encountered in the implementation of the research management guidelines: (1) Limited Knowledge in Research; (2) Much Work Load; (3) Overlapping Activities; and 4) Lack of Resources.

Limited Knowledge in Research. Research for most of the participants interviewed is considered a difficult subject. For them, one of the major challenges they encounter in the implementation of research guidelines was their lack or limited knowledge in research. Although most of them are pursuing their graduate studies and research is one of the major subject, still they do not have really a complete grasp of research which made them anxious in engaging research work.

That is why for them doing research is a negative idea and an additional burden despite that guidelines in doing research in the DepEd were already established.

Teacher 1 emphasized that "*Despite the guidelines of the DepEd, still I am anxious in doing research, I have limited knowledge of it. Research does not interest me.*"

Moreover, Teacher 2 stated that "*I am taking my Masters degree, although I have taken already subjects in research. Still I am not really well verse with research, that is why I hesitate in doing so.*"

According to Teacher 3 "*Since I have a limited knowledge in research, that is why I am always anxious about it. For me its just a burden doing it, it's an added work for me.*"

Much Work Load. All of the participants interviewed agreed that having too much workload as a teacher hinders them from engaging in research. As a teacher, other than teaching a lot of paper works and documentation was added to the usual work. Not to mention also other obligations like ancillary services, chairmanship and coordinators of different programs in school.

As much as they want to engage in research since it is sometimes required or one of the requirements for promotion, they cannot do otherwise because of so many things to do other than teaching duties.

Teacher 1 stated that *“I would really want to participate and do research but, I am preoccupied with so many things such as reports, coordinator ship and committees assigned to me, not to mention my obligation at home. That is why it is difficult for me to engage myself in doing research.”*

“I have once tried to participate in doing research as per guidelines but sadly I have not finished what I started. I can’t focus myself to work for it, because my duties and responsibilities especially I am an adviser and have coordinator ship” said Teacher 2.

In fact, Teacher 3 claimed that *“if only I will be given an ample time and reduced workload... I might have considered engaging myself in research activity”*.

Overlapping Activities. Activities at school and at home, is also one of the things that have been reasoned by the participants. The school has too much activity and usually doing research sometimes is set aside. The participants all agreed that there are many programs and outputs that the Department of Education required for schools and teachers. Not to mention also personal things that teachers prioritize since all of the participants have their own families to take care with. Teacher 3 stated that *“DepEd requires too much of us, since we are not a big school only a few of us facilitated different programs that are required to our school. Programs after programs, report after reports, all of us are involved since again we are a small school”*.

Teacher 2 also highlighted that *“Aside from activities in school, I have also my family to attend to. I am hands on in taking care of my children and what they need that is why doing research is the least of my priority”*.

In support to Teacher 2, Teacher 1 elaborated that *“The division or the district sometimes give us urgent reports and there are activities and programs that will take some time to finish. It cannot be helped that we have to prioritized what is urgent. Though I want to do research since it’s one of the basis for promotion but it always has conflict with other activities.”*

Lack of Resources. According to the participants, research resources are very important. It could be sources for literature, in the form of money or people that would be helpful in doing research. The research management guidelines of the DepEd might have made the conduct of research for DepEd personnel easier and offer financial assistance for accepted research but still according to the participants they would still encounter difficulties in doing it. Not having enough resources for literature, or books/manual in doing research step by step, not to mention the expenses and technical help from experts to help them facilitate the research until it is finish. This is one of the dilemmas of the participants with regard to resources. According to Teacher 2, *“...though the Department of Education offer financial assistance as per experience and according to those who have done research, it was difficult to get the funds, especially in the liquidation process, that is why many are discouraged.”*

Teacher 1 revealed that *“I have difficulty in researching literatures and books that will help me guide in doing research. Since literature is important in writing a research, and it would be better if there is someone knowledgeable to guide us that will serve as our adviser during the whole research process. Because I cannot do it on my own...”*

Teacher 3 also highlighted that *“Research has always been part of our school-based training, but after the training there should be someone who will follow up the things we started so that it will motivate us further. Sources like books in research and access to different literatures is also important. Financial assistance and incentive (laugh) for those who had finish their research should be given so that it will motivate us to engage in research.”*

Conclusions

The teachers in basic education adheres to the guidelines set by the Department in doing research activities in the district. It can be also concluded that there are still areas of improvement in the implementation of this research guidelines. Educational attainment of teachers is a factor to consider in the implementation of the research management guidelines. However, rank of a teacher is not a determining factor of the implementation of research management guidelines.

Teachers should be active in participating in the programs set by the Department of Education especially in the research field. They should response properly in the feed backing process so that their problems in doing research will be properly addressed. If given the opportunity, they should collaborate with the higher ups to ensure their needs and perspectives are incorporated into the research program. Their input will enhance the relevance and practicality of the research. In doing research, they should identify pressing issues and challenges faced by teachers in the current educational landscape. Ensure that the research program addresses topics that are relevant and timely to the teaching profession. They should also attend training sessions for teachers offered by the department to improve their research skills and methodologies. This will not only contribute to the success of the research program but also empower teachers to conduct their own research in the future.

Moreover, the implementation of research management guidelines more specifically doing research in basic education is quite challenging to the participants due to their limited knowledge, skills, and resources. It can also be concluded that the average level of implementation might be contributed by these challenges encountered by the participants.

In formulating and conducting research development program DepEd officials as well as school administrators should establish specific and measurable research goals that align with the needs of teachers and the education system. It should clearly define the research

objectives and the expected outcomes. They should also identify pressing issues and challenges faced by teachers in the current educational landscape. Ensure that the research program addresses topics that are relevant and timely to the teaching profession. They should also ensure that the research program is adequately funded and supported and as much as possible give incentive to those who finished their research. Sufficient resources will enable researchers and teachers to carry out their work effectively.

Lastly, the findings of the study would be an avenue for other researchers and would serve as a reference for future studies. This would also serve as springboard of other related studies that will be conducted.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jessa Marie Lianne C. Balindres

Mary Immaculate Academy, Inc. – Philippines

Garry C. Cachuela

West Visayas State University – Philippines